

PARTICIPATORY BUSINESS MODEL

Experimental approaches to value-creation, value-capturing, and value-delivery that include a broad spectrum of stakeholders. They reflect the process that makes the operations by businesses, organisations, and institutions more desirable, feasible, and financially viable, by leveraging their stakeholder networks. Through such an engaged contribution, participatory business models devise sustainable solutions that strengthen the resilience of the businesses, organisations, institutions, and their networks.

LIVING LABS

Dynamic spaces where ideas and solutions can be co-created, tested, and iterated by collaborating stakeholders. The Living Lab offers methods for cultural heritage institutions, researchers, industry, communities, and government to co-design concrete solutions in real-life environments. Operating as 'innovation zones', Living Labs can bring together community knowledge with professional expertise for action-based projects

KEY ELEMENTS OF PARTICIPATORY BUSINESS MODELLING IN CULTURAL HERITAGE

WHO is engaged in participatory processes and why (value network, its needs, and motivation)?

HOW are participatory processes being executed (participatory practices' forms, frameworks, and activities)?

HOW MUCH value is generated and captured through participatory processes (what value and how is it measured)?

WHAT is the result of the participatory innovation in the business model architecture (a service or product, a process, the location of resources, or even of business models)?

CULTURAL HERITAGE ORGANISATION VALUE CHAIN

The value chain of an organisation is the sum of activities that are carried out to bring a service or a product to consumers, from their ideation and development to their delivery and disposal. Three aspects characterise a value chain: (i) it maps the value creation process at the level of services and activities, not of organisations; (ii) it includes in the analysis all the operations – both backward and forwards – that are necessary to deliver a product or a service, excluding the framework conditions that affect them; and (iii) integrates all the involved stakeholders and their interrelations.

PARTICIPATORY APPROACHES

A set of methods, strategies, and principles that actively involve and engage relevant stakeholders in the planning, decision-making, implementation, and evaluation processes of the project.

They emphasise the importance of inclusivity, collaboration and empowerment, aiming to ensure that all stakeholders have a voice, contribute their knowledge and perspectives, and have a sense of ownership and responsibility over the project.

SUSTAINABLE FINANCING OF CULTURAL HERITAGE INSTITUTIONS

The sustainable financing of cultural heritage organisations is the practice of sustaining their internal operations and fulfilling their role for society, securing their operations' viability, while balancing long-term social, cultural, environmental, and economic goals.